

Statistical Properties of Pure Hindi and Practical Hindi

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Abstract: -Hindi is one of the most spoken language of the world. With the advent of computing in general and the internet in particular, more and more natural languages are being used for information transmission, and Hindi is no exception to it. For computer processing of a natural language, it is essential that the language be encoded in a time and space efficient manner. In this paper, we present the statistical properties of Hindi with respect to two variants of it, pure Hindi and Practical Hindi. The Practical Hindi includes those words also that are commonly used in Hindi but are from other languages like Urdu, English etc. The study is shown to be very helpful in Natural Language Processing (NLP) applications of Hindi.

language. He also developed a bi-lingual (Hindi/English) text editor. Specifically, in the editor, one cannot write wrong Hindi words along with matra symbols.

Sahu and Joshi developed a tool for statistical analysis of pure and practical Hindi words. This work is likely to help in further statistical analysis of the language [2].

Micro-Parsing of Hindi was done by Joshi and Kushwaha [3]. The work aims at finding the flow in the word then propose the alternative potentially useful but structurally correct word.

Index Terms--NLP, Hindi, Statistical Analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

By population, in India, Hindi is the most spoken language. After English, Hindi is the fourth most used language in the world. In spite of this, Hindi is still lagging behind when it comes to computerization.

In Indian's Central Government Organizations, documents are normally in English and Hindi. The documents are easily available in English for processing where as processing of Hindi documents is quite involved.

In modern times, with globalization, most of the natural languages have accepted frequently used words of other languages. This trend has affected Hindi very adversely. If you write/read Hindi you would find that almost 50% words of a paragraph are either from Urdu or from English, written in Devanagari script. With this, it is felt that, to retain the purity of Hindi and to enable easy processing of it, we need to address the information theoretic properties of the language.

In this paper we have developed two corpora, one of Pure Hindi words and the other of Practical Hindi words. Then these corpora are analyzed for various statistical properties.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The work of computerization of Hindi is gaining momentum. In this section we present a comprehensive account of efforts made in this direction.

In his PhD thesis, Joshi [1] developed an assembler and a compiler in Hindi for a C-like

Bharti et al. [4] compared various natural languages through their corpora based on statistical properties. The work includes machine-readable Indian languages using unigram, bigram frequencies etc.

Differences and similarities among Hindi, Punjabi and Nepali was attempted by Bansal et al. [5] This work shows that among these three, Nepali is the most complex.

Jain et al. designed the system UTTAM. [6] The system is supposed to correct the spelling errors. The system was not 100% correct and did not provide the facility of predictive correction.

Cai and Cai [7] took up the challenge of Tibetan information processing considering 2,129,234 words.

In his work, Suen did the work of statistical analysis of English for text processing [8].

Rule based word formation in Hindi was attempted by Joshi and Kushwah [9]. They considered Sandhi and Sandhi- Vichhed on 887 words.

An OCR for Hindi was attempted by Kushwah and Joshi [10] using pixel relationship. In addition to OCR, Kushwah and Joshi developed an algorithm to automatically detect Rola chhand present in Hindi poems [11]. They also proposed Hindi word correction using micro-parsing technique [12].

III. HINDI WORD DICTIONARY

We have developed two separate dictionaries of Hindi words. One dictionary is based on Bhargava Hindi dictionary is [13]. There are 57876 words in total. The other dictionary is developed by collecting

commonly used words in newspapers, web based media, novels etc. This dictionary is called Practical Hindi Dictionary. It has 47587 words.

IV. STATISTICS

We have calculated various statistical parameters for different Hindi words. Statistical parameters of Hindi words include word length, frequency, entropy, probability, standard deviation, and coefficient of variance.

1) Word Length

The assumed length values are shown in Table I, Table II and Table III. Table I shows the length of 13 Hindi vowels. Table II shows the length of the Hindi Matras (Sign). Table III shows the length of 33 Hindi consonants and 3 compound consonants. Various values are computed based on these tables, as examples.

TABLE I: HINDI VOWELS AND THEIR LENGTHS

Vowel	Length of vowel	Vowel	Length of vowel
अ	1	ए	1
आ	1	ऐ	1
ई	1	ओ	1
इ	1	औ	1
उ	1	अं	1
ऊ	1	अः	1

TABLE II: HINDI VOWELS SIGNS AND THEIR LENGTHS

Sign (Matra)	Length of sign	Sign	Length of Sign
ा	1	ै	1
ि	0.5	ो	0.5
ी	1	ौ	1
ु	0.5	ं	0.5
ू	1	ः	1
े	0.5		

TABLE III: HINDI CONSONANTS (VYANNJANA) AND THEIR LENGTHS

	Length		Length		Length		Length		Length
क	1	ख	1	ग	1	घ	1	ङ	1
च	1	छ	1	ज	1	झ	1	ञ	1
ट	1	ठ	1	ड	1	ढ	1	ण	1
त	1	थ	1	द	1	ध	1	न	1
प	1	फ	1	ब	1	भ	1	म	1
य	1	र	1	ल	1	व	1	श	1
ष	1	स	1	ह	1	क्ष	1	त्र	1
ज़	1								

(a) Average Word Length:

TABLE IV: DICTIONARY WORD AND WORD LENGTH

S. No.	Dictionary words	Word length
1	लगभग	4
2	लाख	3
3	वाला	4
4	लोक	3
5	नीचे	3.5
	Total length value	17.5

In Table IV, five words are considered and the word lengths are calculated as discussed in Table I, II and III. Then, average word length is calculated according to the formulae give below:

$$\text{Avg} = \frac{\Sigma \text{word length}}{\text{Total number of words}}$$

Dictionary word and word length shown in Table V. in above example

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Average length} &= 17.5/5 \\ &= 3.5 \end{aligned}$$

(b) Minimum word Length

The minimum length of a word is the minimum alphabetic length of that word. It is clear from Table IV that in two cases the minimum words length is 3.

(c) Maximum word Length:

Maximum word length from Table IV is for words लगभग and वाला. The word length for both

words is 4. In Hindi the longest word length is 32.5 for "लौहपथगामिनिसूचकदर्शकहरितताम्रलौहपट्टिका".

2) Frequency

In this section we have given emphasis on counting letters and words of Hindi dictionary. By counting the number of each letter that appears in the Hindi Bhargava dictionary, we can find out the frequency of meaningful words in Hindi by using the frequency of letters. But there is no repetition of meaningful words in the dictionary, so here we have derived the frequency of the letters. And in future we will also find repetition of meaningful words using Hindi Books, News Papers, Blogs etc.

Frequency is the repetition of a letter/word in a dictionary indicating how often that word is used in communication. Table V shows the maximum frequency count of the letter "ध". The frequency count is 3599. We have worked on Bhargava Hindi dictionary.

3) Probability

We can see the probability of occurrence of words shown in the Table V. probability is based on relative word frequency.

$$\text{Probability } (p(x)) = \text{Word frequency} / \text{Total words}$$

4) Entropy

Information associated with the symbol is "inversely" proportional to the probability of occurrence. The average amount of information per symbol is "Entropy". It is invaluable in NLP. The entropy or the degree of uncertainty of the distribution of a random variable x is computed as:

$$\text{Entropy}(H) = \Sigma p(x) \log_2 (1/p(x)) \text{ bits/symbol}$$

where p(x) represents the probability of x. It measures the amount of information in a random variable.

TABLE V: WORD LENGTHS AND THEIR FREQUENCY-BASED PROBABILITY AND ENTROPY

Word	word length	Practical Dictionary Count (frequency)	frequency in dictionary	Probability	$H = \Sigma p(x) \log_2 (p(x)^{-1})$ bits/symbol
ध	1	3599	1239650	0.002903	0.007365
धन	2	383	430044	0.00089	0.002715
धन्	2.5	59	646357	0.00009	0.000364
धन्य	3.5	25	334424	0.000074	0.000305
धन्यव	4.5	9	164588	0.000054	0.00023
धन्यवा	5	8	160946	0.000049	0.000211
धन्यवाद	6	7	69381	0.0001	0.0004

5) Standard Deviation

The standard deviation is calculated according to the formula,

$$\text{Standard Deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - \bar{X})^2}$$

where:

X_i =Value of the i^{th} point in the data set

\bar{X} =The mean value of the data set

n =The number of data points in the data set

Our dictionary contains total 57876 words which is nothing but N , X_i (individual word length) and \bar{X} average word length of whole dictionary which is 6.32. So, from these our calculated standard deviation is 1.225

6) Coefficient of variation

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Coefficient of variation} &= (\text{Standard Deviation} * 100) / \text{Average Length} \\ &= 19.746 \end{aligned}$$

V. CONCLUSION

We have analyzed the words of Hindi dictionary. We have expansion IV the statistics of Hindi words would be taken up as an extension of the work.

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